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EBOLA: THE MOST DEADLY DISEASE OF MANKIND

Abstracts.

The disease caused by the Ebola virus is considered one of the deadliest diseases known to mankind, as up to 90% of patients lose their lives. Ebola hemorrhagic fever (EVD) is an infectious animal disease that can be transmitted to both humans and non-humans, including primates. The first EVD epidemic occurred in 1976 in the Democratic Republic of Congo. The disease was named "Ebola" because it was found in the Ebola River region of the Congo. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the largest and most complex outbreak of the Ebola virus is the West Africa outbreak that began in early 2014.

Ebola is an acute infectious disease with a severe course with the development of hemorrhagic syndrome and a high mortality rate.

Keywords: *Ebola, disease, mankind*

Etiology

The causative agent of Ebola is an RNA-containing virus and belongs to the Filoviridae family. The virus is divided into five different subtypes or subspecies: Zaire, Sudan, Tai Forest, Bundibugio and Reston. Only the first four of them cause clinically distinct symptoms in humans. Large outbreaks of Ebola hemorrhagic fever in Africa, which have a high mortality rate (up to 90%), are the result of the Zaire, Sudan and Bundibugio subtypes. The severe outbreak that occurred in 2014 and continues to this day in West Africa is caused by the Zaire subtype.[1]

Epidemiology

The main source of infection is wild animals, mainly bats of carnivorous species. They are carriers of the virus, but do not get Ebola themselves. Intermediate hosts are monkeys, rodents, antelopes, and other animals that become infected from bats. In them, the virus causes an outbreak of fever with bleeding and high mortality. [1]

A person can become infected from intermediate hosts during hunting, cutting animal carcasses, eating meat from diseased animals, etc. It can also be transmitted from a sick person to a healthy one through contact with biological fluids (blood, saliva, urine, feces).

In the case of unsafe funeral rites (washing, touching the body of the deceased), infection from the corpse of a person who died of Ebola is possible.

Thus, the sources of infection are both wild animals and already infected people and corpses. Bats are the primary reservoir of the virus.

Clinical features

Due to its unusual and bizarre initial manifestations, which can mimic the symptoms of typhoid fever, malaria, meningococemia, and other bacterial infections, Ebola poses diagnostic challenges.

The incubation period lasts from 2 to 21 days, but symptoms usually appear within 8 to 11 days after infection.[8]

The clinical manifestations of Ebola virus disease have a certain sequence:

1. The initial symptoms are a sudden fever, chills, weakness, muscle pain, and headache. You may also have a sore throat and runny nose.

2. Gastrointestinal disorders - nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, leading to significant dehydration. There may be abdominal pain.

3. Skin rash in 30-50% of cases on the 3rd-7th day of the disease. Often in the form of pinkish spots or hemorrhages.

4. Vascular damage and hemorrhagic syndrome - bleeding from mucous membranes, nosebleeds, hemoptysis, bloody vomiting.

5. Impaired liver and kidney function, encephalopathy, delirium, coma.

6. Outcome of the disease - either recovery in 7-10 days or death from shock and multiple organ failure in 6-16 days.

The mortality rate is 25-90% depending on the strain of the virus, availability of rehydration therapy and care."[2]

Diagnostics

General laboratory data:

- Leukocytosis, neutrophilia, anemia
- Hyponatremia, hypo- or hyperkalemia, hypomagnesemia, hypocalcemia, hypoalbuminemia, hypoglycemia
- Increased creatinine phosphokinase and amylase
- Increase in blood nitrogen, blood urea and creatinine
- Elevated lactate and low serum bicarbonate levels

Specific diagnostics:

In 2014, the WHO recommended that whole blood samples or oral swabs be collected at specialized Ebola treatment centers for laboratory confirmation of the diagnosis. The most commonly used tests are reverse transcription PCR (RT-PCR) and enzyme-linked

immunosorbent assay (ELISA). RT-PCR is able to detect viral RNA in blood samples from infected patients immediately after the onset of symptoms, has a high sensitivity (up to 100%) and a fast result (1-2 days). ELISA detects immunoglobulins G and M in patient samples, but has a lower sensitivity (91%) and is not suitable for initial confirmation during an outbreak.[4]

Treatment

There is no specific treatment for Ebola virus disease. Patients are treated with symptomatic therapy and supportive measures.

The main recommendations for maintenance therapy include the following aspects:

- systematic monitoring and recording of clinical signs and symptoms;
- use of oral rehydration therapy to correct or prevent hypovolemia;
- administration of parenteral fluids for patients who cannot receive enough fluids enterally;
- performing biochemical analysis of blood serum and correction of detected electrolyte disorders;
- ensuring normal oxygen saturation with oxygen therapy;
- the use of intravenous vasoactive drugs to treat patients with hypotension that does not respond to fluid therapy and signs of insufficient organ perfusion;
- treatment of pain, use of antiemetics and anxiolytics;
- providing nutritional support, taking into account the individual needs of the patient, including intravenous glucose administration to correct hypoglycemia if necessary;
- use of microbiological analysis to guide antimicrobial prescribing. In cases where this is not possible, broad-spectrum antibiotics and antimalarials are recommended, taking into account the geographical context and symptoms.[6,7]

Prevention

Prevention of the Ebola virus includes the following measures:

1. Sanitary and epidemiological measures: early detection and hospitalization of patients, isolation of suspected cases, monitoring of contacts, safe burial of the dead.
2. Personal protective equipment for healthcare workers and other persons in contact with patients. It is mandatory to use gloves, masks, goggles, overalls, and avoid contact with the patient's bodily fluids.
3. Disinfection measures in hospitals and places where patients stay. Disinfecting surfaces with disinfectants, disinfecting biological secretions, linen, and instruments.

4. Health education of the population on the ways of spreading the virus, prevention measures and the need to seek medical care.

5. Development of vaccines and medicines for specific prevention and treatment of the disease. rVSV-ZEBOV is the only vaccine approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the prevention of Ebola virus disease.

Compliance with these measures can prevent the spread of Ebola and save lives.

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